

Recommended citation: Tiili, J. (2019). Sharing Good Practices for Enhancing Introductory Physics Learning. In Nagyn, B. V., Murphy, M., Järvinen, H.-M., & Kálmán, A. (Eds.), *Varietas delectat... Complexity is the new normality. SEFI 47th Annual Conference* (pp. 2106-2106). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Budapest, Hungary. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14657466.

SHARING GOOD PRACTICES FOR ENHANCING INTRODUCTORY PHYSICS LEARNING

J. Tiili

Tampere University of Applied Sciences, Finland

Topics: Fundamentals of Engineering Education: Mathematics and Physics

Keywords: Engineering physics

Introductory engineering physics is usually a part of the very first studies that engineering students encounter in their studies. Natural sciences and mathematics form the base of engineering and technology, but for some students these introductory courses can be a real threshold and a motivation killer to their studies. Most of the dropouts drop out at the beginning of studies. There are a lot of reasons why students drop out, but is there something that we as engineering educators are able to do in this very sensitive early part of students' studies? Do we already have some good practices to tackle the problem?

Expected learning outcomes of introductory engineering physics vary a lot depending on the degree program and the level of studies. Students entering the universities have very heterogeneous skills in physics, mathematics and other natural sciences.

Part 1:

In the workshop, the participants are first asked to recognize and describe the starting point and the goal of students' skills in physics. The variations of these skills (in the beginning and at the end of engineering physics) are discussed and compared among participants and some common conclusions are drawn out.

Part 2:

After the conclusions, participants are divided in small groups on basis of part 1 so that they are able to discuss with people with same kind of challenges. The second part of workshop is to share ideas and experiences. What actions there have been made to enhance students' learning outcomes in introductory engineering physics in participants' universities? What kind of personal changes in teaching there have been made for the same goal? Is there still something that participants would like to try?

Part 3:

The good practices rising from these small groups are documented, collected and presented at the end of workshop.